

Influence of Higher Education on Empowering Women in West Bengal

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Abstract

This study explores the socioeconomic and cultural environment with an emphasis on women's empowerment through higher education in West Bengal, India. Women in West Bengal still struggle with issues of gender inequality, restricted access to resources, and limited participation in decision-making processes, despite significant progress. This study investigates how women's empowerment and gender equality are advanced in the area through higher education. The study clarifies the relationship between women's empowerment and higher education by exploring theoretical frameworks, empirical investigations, and literature. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, drawing on both qualitative and quantitative analysis to comprehend the mechanisms by which women's empowerment in West Bengal is facilitated by higher education. The results show that women's empowerment and higher education are positively correlated, with education providing a means for women in West Bengal to achieve economic, social, and political empowerment. However, obstacles like unequal access, gender prejudice, and cultural norms continue to persist and restrict women's empowerment and active engagement in higher education. In summary, the report emphasizes how critical it is to give top priority to programs that expand women's access to higher education and foster an inclusive workplace culture. West Bengal can keep moving towards gender parity and realizing the potential of its female population by eliminating these obstacles.

Keywords: Higher education, Women's Empowerment, West Bengal, Gender inequality, Socioeconomic development

Introduction:

In the socioeconomic and cultural context of West Bengal, India, women's empowerment is a major concern. Women in West Bengal still confront several obstacles linked to gender inequity, restricted access to resources, and limited participation in decision-making processes, even with recent advancements. In this manner, higher education shows itself to be a potent instrument for advancing gender equality and women's empowerment.

Women's lives are transformed by higher education since it gives them the information, skills, and chances for both professional and personal development. It not only increases their financial independence but also gives them the confidence to question social conventions, go for leadership positions, and make significant contributions to their communities. Higher education acts as a catalyst for women's empowerment in West Bengal, where historical and cultural obstacles prevent women's growth and generate an inclusive and democratic society. If women are educated and have access to higher education, which acts as a gateway to productive employment, they can contribute significantly to society. Women are widely acknowledged to make major contributions to society, as stated in the eighth five-year plan of India (1992–1997). It has become widely recognized that women's engagement in the manufacturing, service, and agricultural sectors contributes significantly to the economy (Maity&Sanuar, 2020).

The purpose of this research study is to investigate how women's empowerment in West Bengal is impacted by higher education. The study aims to comprehend how higher education affects several aspects of women's lives, such as economic, social, and political empowerment, by looking at the connection of education, gender, and empowerment. The research will clarify the mechanisms by which women's empowerment in the region is facilitated by higher education, utilizing a blend of qualitative insights and quantitative analysis.

Objectives:

To evaluate the state of women's empowerment in West Bengal, paying particular attention to significant parameters including work, education, and involvement in decision-making to evaluate how women's empowerment in West Bengal is aided by higher education, considering socioeconomic outcomes, skill development, and educational accessibility. To determine the obstacles and chances that women in West Bengal face in achieving the goal of higher education, including expectations from society, financial limitations, and gender bias. Through qualitative interviews or focus groups, investigate women's experiences and perceptions of how higher education affects their empowerment.

Literature Review:

Extensive research and intellectual inquiry have been conducted on women's empowerment and higher education, both internationally and in regional contexts such as West Bengal, India. This review of the literature offers a summary of important theoretical frameworks and empirical research that investigate from different angles, the relation between women's empowerment and higher education.

Conceptual Structures:

Capital theory: By the principles of the Human Capital Theory, women's human capital in West Bengal is greatly enhanced by higher education. Women who receive an education benefit from enhanced work prospects, greater incomes, and greater socioeconomic mobility, all of which ultimately contribute to their empowerment in the community (Ross, 2023).

Capability Approach:

Amartya Sen proposed the capacity approach, which emphasizes the moral significance of people's freedom to pursue well-being. It evaluates people's quality of life not just by looking at their money or subjective well-being, but also by looking at their real capacity to do and be what they value. This method emphasizes the importance of interpersonal differences and the function of social structures in supporting human flourishing. It centers on comprehending the actual opportunities people have to develop lifestyles they have cause to value (Amartya Sen's Capability Theory Approach, 2020).

Gender and Development Theory: This framework emphasizes how important it is to address gender differences in the processes of development. One way to challenge traditional structures and conventions, enable women to stand up for their rights, and promote gender equality is through higher education.

Empirical Studies:

"The Impact of Higher Education on Women's Empowerment in Developing Countries": This study concentrates on how education improves women's autonomy, decision-making ability, and socioeconomic standing in developing nations. It examines the relationship between these two phenomena (Kabeer, 2005).

"Women's Higher Education and Economic Empowerment: Insights from Bangladesh": This study looks at the relationship in Bangladesh between women's economic empowerment and higher education. According to research, women's economic empowerment is facilitated by obtaining a higher education, which gives them the self-assurance and ability to pursue commercial activities (Hossain, 2019).

Regional Perspectives:

"A study on the present status of Women in Higher Education of Purba and Paschim Medinipur" This case study explores the effects of higher education on women's empowerment in West Bengal's Purba and Paschim Medinipur, with an emphasis on the socioeconomic consequences and obstacles that women encounter when attempting to pursue and complete higher education (Maity, 2021).

"Women's Access to Higher Education in West Bengal In Open Distance Learning System": West Bengal has experienced a dramatic change in the way people view higher education as a means of empowering women in recent years. This case study examines how programs like open distance education, especially those offered by establishments like the Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), have a transforming effect on women's access to higher education and the advancement of their socioeconomic status (Maity & Sanuar, 2020).

Overall, the research shows the importance of higher education in empowering women through increasing their capacity, improving their socioeconomic prospects, and reducing gender inequality. However, obstacles like unequal access, sex discrimination, and cultural norms remain in preventing women's active participation and empowerment in higher education.

Methodology

Secondary data has been gathered for this study and descriptive approaches have been employed. The data and material used in this study came from a variety of sources, including books, research articles, magazines, research journals, e-journals, and reports from UGC and the higher education departments of West Bengal and India. Secondary data serve as the study's foundation. Several indicators are used to compare the state of women in West Bengal to the rest of India, including Female Literacy (FL), Female Gross Enrolment Ratio, and the distribution of West Bengal colleges by year about India.

Year	West Bengal	Growth Rate	% Growth Rate	India	Growth Rate	% Growth Rate
1971.00	26.56			18.70		
1981.00	36.56	10.00	27.35	24.80	7.88	31.77
1991.00	46.56	10.00	21.48	39.42	9.44	23.95
2001.00	60.22	13.66	22.68	53.67	14.87	27.71
2011.00	71.16	10.94	15.37	65.46	11.30	17.26

Source: Census data (1971-2011)

The table shows the growth of female literacy rates in West Bengal and India from 1971 to 2011. West Bengal had a 26.56% female literacy rate in 1971, growing at a pace of 6.29%. In India, 18.7% of women were literate, and this percentage was growing at a rate of 6.63%. With a growth rate of 10%, West Bengal's female literacy rate rose to 36.56% by 1981. In India, it increased at a pace of 7.88% to reach 24.8%. The female literacy rate in West Bengal increased by 13.66%, from 46.56% to 60.22%, between 1991 and 2001. On the other hand, India's female literacy rate increased by 14.87%, from 39.42% to 53.67%. Finally, West Bengal's female literacy rate grew by 10.94% between 2001 and 2011, rising from 60.22% to 71.16%. With an 11.3% growth rate, the female literacy rate in India increased from 53.67% to 65.46%.

	West Bengal			India		
	Male	Female	Both	Male	Female	Both
2015	19.1	16.2	17.7	25.4	23.5	24.5
2016	19.8	17.2	18.5	26	24.5	25.2
2017	19.9	17.6	18.7	26.3	25.4	25.8
2018	20	18.7	19.3	26.3	26.4	26.3
2019	20.3	19.6	19.9	26.9	27.3	27.1
2020	20.3	22.3	21.3	26.7	27.9	27.3
2021	25.9	26.8	26.3	28.3	28.5	28.4

Source: AISHE, Report (2015-2021)

The table shows a comparison of the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) between West Bengal and India from 2015 to 2021. In West Bengal, the GER for male was 19.1% in 2015, 16.2% for female, and 17.7% for both genders combined. In contrast, the GER in India was 25.4% for males, 23.5% for females, and 24.5% for both genders combined. In West Bengal, the GER increased significantly by 2016 to 19.8% for male, 17.2% for female, and 18.5% for both genders combined. Additionally, there was a minor increase in the GER in India, where it was 26% for male, 24.5% for female, and 25.2%

for both genders together. India's GER was 26.3% for males, 25.4% for females, and 25.8% for both genders together, whereas West Bengal's GER was 19.9% for males, 17.6% for females, and 18.7% for both genders together. West Bengal's GER increased to 20% for male, 18.7% for Female, and 19.3% for the two sexes combined in 2018. In contrast, the GER in India was 26.3% for male, 26.4% for female, and 26.3% for both sexes combined. The GER continued to increase in both West Bengal and India in subsequent years, with the figures fluctuating slightly. In 2021, the gender-specific GER in West Bengal was 25.9% for male, 26.8% for female, and 26.3% for both genders combined. overall contrast, the GER overall India was 28.3% for male, 28.5% for female, and 28.4% for both genders when combined. While West Bengal's GER has generally grown over time, it has stayed marginally below India's national average, indicating that the state is still working to raise enrolment rates.

Gender disparity in work participation rate in Major states of India						
State	Participation rate				Change	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
	2001	2011	2001	2011		
Andhra Pradesh	56.2	57	35.1	36.2	0.8	1.1
Assam	49.9	53.6	20.7	22.5	3.7	1.8
Bihar	47.4	46.5	18.8	19.1	-0.9	0.3
Gujarat	54.9	57.2	27.9	23.4	2.3	-4.5
Haryana	50.3	50.4	27.2	17.8	0.1	-9.4
Himachal Pradesh	54.6	58.7	43.7	44.8	4.1	1.1
Karnataka	56.6	59	32	31.9	2.4	-0.1
Kerala	50.2	52.7	15.4	18.2	2.5	2.8
Madhya Pradesh	51.5	53.6	33.2	32.6	2.1	-0.6
Maharashtra	53.3	56	30.8	31.1	2.7	0.3
Odisha	52.5	56.1	24.7	27.2	3.6	2.5
Punjab	53.6	55.2	19.1	13.9	1.6	-5.2
Rajasthan	50	51.5	33.5	35.1	1.5	1.6
Tamil Nadu	57.6	59.3	31.5	31.8	1.7	0.3
Uttar Pradesh	46.8	47.7	16.5	16.7	0.9	0.2
West Bengal	54	57.1	18.3	18.1	3.1	-0.2

Source: Census data (2001-2011)

The table provides insights into the gender disparity in work participation rates across major states of India from 2001 to 2011. From 2001 to 2011, West Bengal's rates of work participation by gender were usually more equitable than those of other states. Compared to several other states, West Bengal has comparatively greater rates of involvement for both males and females. The state continued to have a smaller gender disparity in employment than states like Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Punjab, and Gujarat. During this time, the gender gap widened in several states, although gender parity remained largely stable or even significantly improved in West Bengal. In West Bengal, however, there was a minor decline in the proportion of women working between 2001 and 2011, suggesting that focused initiatives are required to preserve or advance gender parity in the workforce. Comparing West Bengal's performance to many other major Indian states throughout the required period, the state did well overall in terms of gender inequality in labour participation rates.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data
Growth of Female Literacy Rate from 1971-2011

Comparison of Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) of West Bengal and India

Gender disparity in work participation rate in Major states of

India

Discussion:

Even though West Bengal's female literacy rate has increased, there is still a critical need to improve women's access to higher education. Although the state's labour participation rates are reasonably equitable when compared to other states, there has been a slight decrease in the number of female workers. These results highlight the significance of focused initiatives to advance gender equality in the workplace and education, highlighting the revolutionary potential of higher education in empowering women in West Bengal.

Conclusion:

This study highlights the advancements made in West Bengal in increasing the rates of female literacy and encouraging fair work participation. However, there are still issues, especially with maintaining women's participation in the workforce and providing them with greater access to higher education. Although West Bengal has made great progress towards gender equality, more has to be done to address the underlying inequalities and impediments that prevent women from achieving full equality. West Bengal can move closer to attaining gender parity and using the full potential of its female population by giving priority to programs that increase educational opportunities and create a welcoming environment for women in the workforce.

Reference

1. AISHE. Report, MHRD. Retrieved from <https://aishe.gov.in/aishe/gotoAisheReports>
2. Alam, M. J., Ogawa, K., Basharat, L., & Ahsan, A. H. M. (2023). Significance of Quality Higher Education in the Advancement of Gender Equality: The Case of Bangladesh. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 2050-7003
3. Amartya Sen's Capability Theory Approach. (2020, April 11). UCAV. Retrieved from <https://www.cmiuniversal.com/en/amartya-sens-capability-theory-approach>
4. Census of India (2011). West Bengal Population Sex Ratio. Retrieved from <https://www.census2011.co.in/census/state/west+bengal.html>
5. Kabeer, N. (2005). Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment: A Critical Analysis of the Third Millennium Development Goal. *Gender and Development*, 13(1), 13-24. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20053132>
6. Maity, A., & Sanuar, S. (2020). Women's Access to Higher Education in West Bengal in Open Distance Learning System. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 7(3), 73. Retrieved from <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v7i9/ART2019939.pdf>
7. Maity, A., & Sanuar, S. (2020). Women's Access to Higher Education in West Bengal in Open Distance Learning System. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 7(3), 73. Retrieved from <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2003015.pdf>
8. Maity, V. (2021). A Study on the Present Status of Women in Higher Education of Purba & Paschim Medinipur. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 2(7), 1551-1558. Retrieved from <https://www.ijrpr.com/uploads/V2ISSUE7/IJRPR768.pdf>
9. Ross, S. (2023, September 17). What Is the Human Capital Theory and How Is It Used? Investopedia.
10. Sarkar, S. (2021). Empowerment of Women in West Bengal: Issues and Challenges. *Inclusive and Sustainable Development*, 129-158. Serials Publications Pvt Ltd. Retrieved from [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355444061_Empowerment_of_Women_in_West_Bengal_Issues_and_Challenges#:~:text=Scheme%20for%20Empowerment%20of%20Adolescent,accessing%20public%20services%2C%20etc\).](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355444061_Empowerment_of_Women_in_West_Bengal_Issues_and_Challenges#:~:text=Scheme%20for%20Empowerment%20of%20Adolescent,accessing%20public%20services%2C%20etc).)
11. Taxak, P. (2013). Women Empowerment Through Higher Education. *Research Analysis and Evaluation International Indexed & Refereed Research Journal*, IV(40),. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/5823068/Women_Empowerment_Through_Higher_Education